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History of Sport

NEW APPROACHES TO PHYSICAL UPBRINGING OF YOUTH IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article analyzes the physical activity of youth in Russia. It is shown that sport has a universal ability to solve problems of increasing the level of public health, increasing the life expectancy of the population, and is also an effective way to prevent asocial manifestations. However, according to official statistics, the number of systematically engaged in sports and recreational activities in Russia is significantly lower than similar indicators in developed Western countries.

The most important tasks in this direction are the restoration of the best traditions of the physical culture and sports movement of past years and the search for new effective mechanisms for the development of mass sports with the participation of representatives of various socio-demographic groups of society.

Keywords: sport, education, skills, person, state.

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of education and personality formation is exacerbated by the social conditions of modern life. Russia is experiencing a deep and multilateral crisis of transition to a new qualitative state: the old system of spiritual values and guidelines is deformed; the system of false values is spreading by means of “mass” culture: consumerism, the cult of power, aggression, freedom without responsibility.

In social life today, the striving for wealth and comfort has a significant share, the ideals of collectivism are supplanted by individualism, the values of former selfless service (to the Fatherland, science, art) - the principle of personal gain.

Changes in the values of people limit the development of their spiritual world. The socio-economic changes taking place in the country, their complexity, inconsistency and lack of scientific justification aggravates the problem of the formation and development of the spirituality of the citizen of modern society, the priority of spiritual education, which objectively necessitate the need to change the educational strategy in educational institutions.

In the course of modern transformations of life, improving social and political relations, new approaches are needed to educate the personality of students, the formation of the foundations of humanism, morality, industry, responsibility, physical, socio-cultural development, their integral manifestation.

II. METHODOLOGY

The following methods were used to solve the tasks in the article: theoretical analysis of literature on philosophy, psychology, pedagogy and ethnopedagogy, history, reflecting the current state of the problem; discrete and included monitoring of the educational work of young men, organized according to a special program; questionnaires, interviews and conversations with trainers, teachers, students and their parents; experimental work.

III. DISCUSSION

The issues of raising children cannot be considered outside the real processes of life and life of the people, their geographical, historical and socio-economic conditions that determine the uniqueness of national traditions, customs and rites. A great contribution to the study of this problem was made by V.F. Afanasyev, A.L. Bugaev, G.N. Volkov, A.Sh. Gashimov, B.A. Kadyrov, V.P. Kochnev, Sh.A. Mirzoev, A.P. Orlova, T.N. Petrova, I.S. Portnyagin, V.I. Prokopenko, N.V. Silistraru, I.I. Khanbikov, N.K. Shamaev, I.A. Shorov and others. Cultural-historical, spiritual-national educational traditions are contained in the works of V.F. Afanasyeva, U.A. Vinokurova, A.A. Grigorieva, D.A. Danilova, A.G. Kornilova, N.D. Neustroeva, A.P. Okoneshnikova, B.N. Popova, I.S. Portnyagina, A.D. Semenova, K.S. Chiryayeva and others. In their works it is shown that the appeal to ethnic spiritual wealth is the key to an effective solution to the problems of education.

The centuries-old traditions of the Russian education system (the unity of instruction and upbringing, intellectual and moral, professional and sociocultural development of the individual, etc.), its humanistic positions are disclosed in the works of V.I. Vernadsky, P.A. Florensky, D.N. Uznadze, M.M. Bakhtin, G.G. Shpeta, M.K. Mamardashvili and others. They create the prerequisites for building education on integrative processes. Integrative trends are reflected in studies of an integrated approach to education and training (Yu.K. Babansky, A.P. Belyaeva, M.N. Berulava, B.S. Gershunsky, E.M. Monoszon, etc.); developmental training and education (D.V. Vilkeev, G.I. Ibragimov, G.D. Kirillova, B.T. Likhachev, P.I. Pidkasisty, A.A. Pinsky, V.G. Razumovsky, N.A. Polovnikova, Yu.S. Tyunnikov and others). In the theory of physical education and sports, the concept of physical activity was developed (V.K. Balsevich); views on the content, means and methods of education in physical education (B.A. Ashmarin, L.P. Matveev, R.Kh. Yarullin and others); the theory of physical culture of personality (M.Ya. Vilensky, V.M. Vydrin, S.D. Neverkovich, N.I. Ponomarev, V.I. Stolyarov, etc.), the relationship of physical education with intellectual, moral, moral and ethical .

IV. RESULTS

Based on the fact that one of the most important tasks facing the field of education is the formation of a spiritually rich person who is open, ready for self-creation and inclusion in social development, it is necessary to create optimal organizational and pedagogical conditions in educational institutions that need to be managed effectively. By management, we understand the deliberate impact on the control object, ensuring that they perform the actions necessary to achieve their goals.

Regarding the object and subject of our research, management is an expedient activity aimed at streamlining the educational process in physical education and sports activities.

Based on the analysis of the state of the problem in historical, psychological and pedagogical literature, the features of the development of modern society are identified that determine the spiritual world of people and affect the spiritual and moral development of the individual, the conceptual foundations of the bodily and spiritual development of man and the integration of spiritual and physical education, where the person is organic, open, dynamic, self-organizing subsystem of society and nature.

The patterns of integration of spiritual and physical education (psychosomatic and sociocultural unity of a person; physical culture is one of the components of the general culture of a person, stimulating the development of other personal qualities; a person develops himself by appropriate culture, upbringing helps in self-creation of a person) are determined by motives, value orientations, needs as internal regulators of personality, where a human-creating process is carried out, strengthening the spiritual, moral and physical the young man's. The study confirmed the phenomenon known in practice: sport exposes both the strengths and weaknesses of the spiritual and moral qualities of a person; often, some of them develop negative qualities, such as aggressiveness, cruelty related to anti-spirituality. Traditionally for the culture of Western Europe, the physical development of a person is based on the idea of universal values of the soul and body. In the modern Western European concepts of physical culture, the so-called post-material idea has already begun to take shape, which, continuing the traditions of humanism, rationalism and individualism, proceeded from the real processes of Western society.

Sport is popular

- Sport plays an important role in our life. There are many stadiums and public sport facilities in Russia.
- Numerous national and international matches and competitions are regularly held in our country. They attract large numbers of fans. Most of the important games are shown on TV.
- Television has made sport available to all.
- Many fitness clubs and public leisure centers have been built during the past years.

The formation of the conceptual foundations of physical culture in feudal and post-reform Russia has repeatedly become the subject of a number of studies. They rightly noted the original ideas of Russian figures about physical education, traced the connection with the achievements of popular pedagogical science, cited numerous historical facts, especially in the late XIX-early XX centuries, etc. However, personal enthusiasm, unavailability of some research materials for Soviet specialists, forced to give a one-sided approach to historical

facts and other objective and subjective reasons, in our opinion, did not contribute to solving the problem of holistic self-regulation of the modern approach to the concept of physical culture. The distinctive features of Russian physical culture, as well as the cultural sphere as a whole, are caused by the historical process. Young thousand-year-old Russian civilization absorbed much of the experience of neighboring countries.

This gave rise to a widespread opinion, especially in European and North American specialized literature, that Russian culture is a kind of transition type of Euro-Asian culture. Some generalizing work on processes in world physical culture also come from this postulate. We adhere to different point of view Russian culture, including physical, identity, based on the interweaving of different cultures, enriched by its own historical experience. It is physical culture that represents the social factor of effective influence on the process of physical development and improvement of a person, which allows for the directed formation of his vital physical qualities and abilities. The physically normal state of a person (which is just violated when there is a lack or limited physical activity) acts as the basis of social activity of a person.

Russian kinds of sport

Physical education is associated with a special kind of physical activity. This type of physical, motor activity in the form of physical exercises has an educational function, it develops not only the body of the subject, but also is associated with its behavior as a person. Consequently, the physical in man plays the role of mechanisms by which his social functions are realized.

V. CONCLUSION

Sport today has become an integral part of various segments of the social life of individuals. Modern culture exerts unprecedented pressure on people, forcing them to be, or at least look athletic. Sport as a specific type of human activity combines the various aspects of human existence and therefore should be considered in the unity of the spiritual and physical.

Its main goal is the improvement of man through the harmonization of physical, aesthetic and moral development. At the same time, competitive activity should serve as a demonstration of the possibilities of a harmoniously developed human body in conditions of non-antagonistic confrontation.

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НОВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ФИЗИЧЕСКОМУ ВОСПИТАНИЮ МОЛОДЁЖИ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье анализируется физическая активность молодежи в России. Показано, что спорт обладает универсальной способностью решать проблемы повышения уровня общественного здоровья, увеличения продолжительности жизни населения, а также является эффективным способом предотвращения асоциальных проявлений.

Однако, согласно официальной статистике, количество систематически занимающихся спортивно-оздоровительными мероприятиями в России значительно ниже аналогичных показателей в развитых западных странах. Важнейшими задачами в этом направлении являются восстановление лучших традиций физкультурно-спортивного движения прошлых лет и поиск новых эффективных механизмов развития массового спорта с участием представителей различных социально-демографических групп общества.

Ключевые слова: спорт, образование, навыки, личность, государство.

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